

N responsiveness of promising rice cultivars for submergence-prone rainfed lowlands in eastern India

A. Ghosh, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, India
Email: riceghosh@yahoo.com

Rice under submergence-prone lowland conditions suffers from meager productivity. Growing traditional tall cultivars, which do not respond well to N application, appears to be one of the major constraints to high productivity. The advent of high-yielding varieties, with their better N responsiveness, requires adequate N fertilization as it becomes imperative to promote their submergence tolerance ability under these waterlogged conditions (Ghosh 2000). One major setback of N application under this uncontrolled hydrological conditions is low recovery, barely exceeding 25–30% (Mohanty et al 1999). Taking these ecological barriers into account, there is a need to develop varieties that show a fairly greater response to N application under submergence-prone environments.

A field experiment was conducted during three consecutive wet seasons (2002–04) at the Central Rice Research Institute, India, to study the relative N responsiveness of promising deepwater rice genotypes. Soil at the experimental site was alluvial sandy clay loam, with 0.83% organic C and 0.09% total N. In the first year, 10 promising deepwater rice cultivars and 10 tall, photoperiod-sensitive, long-duration (175–180 d) varieties collected from different states in eastern India were compared with national check Sabita. Genotypes producing more than 1.0 t grain ha⁻¹ were considered for further field evaluation during the second year, as grain yield from this ecology averages 2 t ha⁻¹ ± 0.5 (Catling 1992). In subsequent yield confirmatory trials, seven such genotypes were further tested in the third year, directly sown in mid-May. The recommended dose of NPK (40, 8.8, and 16.6 kg ha⁻¹) was applied at sowing only and was compared with the no-N treatment. N was applied in combination—75% from a chemical source (urea) and 25% from an organic source (farmyard manure). The experiment was laid out in a split-plot randomized design (two levels of N in main plots and seven genotypes in subplots) with three replications.

Occurrences of monsoon rain and subsequent flooding patterns remained more or less the same during the 3-year study. Every year, the monsoon rains came in the third week of June; rainfall distribution was more or less normal, 1,500–1,600 mm over the crop-growing months. Water started accumulating in late June, its depth rising to a maximum of 97–100 cm in late August, when

cultivars grew to 90–100-cm height and were fully or partially submerged. Nonetheless, all cultivars, except for Ambica, Rayada B3, Purnendu, Hansheswari, Durga, OR877-ST, CR662-2211, and Sabita, soon lodged after the water receded during the grain-filling stage, resulting in fewer effective tillers and poor grain yield.

The data showed a consistently positive impact of N application on plant growth and vigor, promoting plant elongation and robustness to a significantly greater degree than the no-N treatment. Overall, plant height at harvest increased by around 3% more than these of plants without N. This was more pronounced in Ambica, the tallest of all cultivars tested (Table 1). Ghosh and Sharma (1999) reported the beneficial effects of N application on promoting plant elongation, which is critical in enabling deepwater rice varieties to thrive better in prolonged waterlogged conditions. Cultivars that were less than 100 cm tall performed miserably at the onslaught of flood in the first year. They produced fewer panicles and had less weight, resulting in poor grain yield (<1 t ha⁻¹); these were not considered for further study in the following years.

Table 1. Effect of N level on plant height (cm) of rice cultivars under submergence-prone rainfed lowland conditions (av of 3 y).

Cultivar \ N level	N ₀	N ₄₀	Mean
Ambica	168	173	171
Rayada B3	143	148	146
Purnendu	122	127	125
Hansheswari	141	146	144
Durga	143	148	146
OR877-ST	143	148	146
CR662-2211	144	149	147
Sabita	137	142	140
CD (<i>P</i> = 0.05)			
Between N levels		3.00	
Between cultivars		2.50	

The varying degrees of N responsiveness were reflected in the grain yields of cultivars, accounting for a 54.14% yield advantage over no N application (Table 2). Bangura (1987) reported the same advantages of N application under excess-water conditions. With both levels of N application, Durga produced consistently higher grain yield over the years, 1.95 t ha⁻¹ without N and 2.95 t ha⁻¹ with 40 kg N ha⁻¹. Accordingly, the highest mean grain yield across all N applications was observed in Durga (2.45 t ha⁻¹), which yielded 15.56% more than Sabita. Considering grain yield at N₄₀, the cultivars could be ranked as follows:

Durga>Ambica>OR877-ST>CR662-2211>Sabita>Rayada B3>Purnendu>Hansheswari; at N₀, a slight deviation occurred: Durga>Sabita>Ambica>OR877-ST>CR662-2211>Rayada B3>Hansheswari>Purnendu.

Table 2. Effect of N level on grain yield (t ha⁻¹) of rice cultivars under submergence-prone rainfed lowland condition (av of 3 y).

Cultivar	N level		Mean
	N ₀	N ₄₀	
Ambica	1.70	2.84	2.27
Rayada B3	1.50	2.41	1.96
Purnendu	1.05	1.69	1.37
Hansheswari	1.20	1.51	1.36
Durga	1.95	2.95	2.45
OR877-ST	1.70	2.80	2.25
CR662-2211	1.65	2.76	2.20
Sabita	1.80	2.43	2.12
CD (<i>P</i> = 0.05)			
Between N levels		0.59	
Between cultivars		0.38	

In accordance with their productivity variation, agronomic N-use efficiency (NUE) also showed significant variation among all genotypes, with relatively better NUE in Ambica, CR662-2211, OR877-ST, and Durga (Table 3). Overall, NUE ranged from as low as 7.75 kg grain kg⁻¹ N ha⁻¹ in Hansheswari to as high as 28.5 kg grain kg⁻¹ N ha⁻¹ in Ambica (Ghosh and Jha 2002).

Table 3. N-use pattern of rice cultivars as influenced by N management under submergence-prone rainfed lowland conditions (av of 3 y).

Cultivar	N utilization pattern	N-use efficiency* (kg grain kg N ⁻¹ ha ⁻¹)	N uptake(kg ha ⁻¹)		N recovery (%)
			N ₀	N ₄₀	
Ambica		28.50	40.80	52.75	29.87
Rayada B3		22.75	37.50	48.30	27.00
Purnendu		16.00	35.00	45.50	26.25
Hansheswari		7.75	30.50	40.00	23.75
Durga		25.00	39.25	50.55	28.25
OR877-ST		27.50	40.30	52.00	29.25
CR662-2211		27.75	42.25	55.50	33.12
Sabita		15.75	35.00	45.00	25.00
CD (<i>P</i> = 0.05)		3.25	0.75	1.15	1.75

*NUE at an application rate of 40 kg N ha⁻¹.

N uptake increased with increasing N application, which ranged from 40.00 to 55.50 kg ha⁻¹ in plants at N₄₀ and from 30.50 to 42.25 kg ha⁻¹ in plants at N₀. At both N levels, N uptake was maximum in CR662-2211, Ambica, OR877-ST, and Durga. Overall, N recovery was within the 23.75–33.12% range; it was maximum in CR662-2211, Ambica, OR 877-ST, and Durga (Mohanty et al 1999).

The data show that growing N-responsive cultivars under submergence-prone conditions can enhance grain yield. Durga, Ambica, OR877-ST, and CR662-2211 are the more promising varieties/cultivars in this regard.

References

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